

Household Water Sample Collection CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
3	Visit	Baseline Visit Follow-up Visit 1 Follow-up Visit 2 Follow-up Visit 3
4	Sample ID	
5	Sample Type?	Stored Drinking water (go to Q5a) Stored Household water (go to Q5a) Stored Other water (go to Q5a) Source water (go to Q6) Rinse (hand) water (go to Q7)
5a	If STORED water, what was the water stored in?	Plastic bucket no lid Plastic bucket with lid Plastic bucket with tap and no lid Plastic bucket with tap and lid Metal bucket (covered) Metal bucket (uncovered) Clay pot (covered) Clay pot (uncovered) Jerry can Drum Other (specify)
6	What was the source of the water?	Tap inside house (go to Q8) Tap outside house (go to Q8) Borehole Kiosk Bottled River Other
6a	What was the GPS location of the source – if collected outside the house?	Latitude Longitude GPS reference number
6b	Were you taken to the source by a household member??	Yes (go to Q8) No (go to Q8)
7	If RINSE water, how many people washed their hands in the sample	1 2 3

		4 5 More than 5
7a	Scan their Participant IDs	
8	Was 500ml collected	Yes No
	<p><i>You have completed data collection for this sample.</i></p> <p><i>Please collect 4 water samples where possible, including source, stored and rinse water.</i></p>	
9	Staff signature	
10	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY